

Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District

Anggriyani¹, Bulkani²

¹Elementary school 1 Setiap. Kalimantan Selatan. Indonesia

²Master of Elementary Education. Universitas Muhammadiyah Palangkaraya. Indonesia

ABSTRACT

Published Online: November 27, 2024

The development of technology in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 requires teachers to use technology in classroom learning. However, there are difficulties for teachers in applying the application, namely: (1) teachers have difficulty in adapting to technological developments; (2) classroom learning must be adaptive; (3) teachers have difficulty adapting to technology; and (4) teachers have difficulty in utilizing existing technology. One of the applications used by teachers in sharing good practices is that teachers must use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM), this application is a development provided by the Ministry of Education, as one of the suggestions prepared by the government in implementing classroom learning. The facts show that there are still many teachers who have not been able to adapt to this PPM, especially in the findings in social studies learning in elementary schools in Pandawan. in the subject of Social Sciences (IPS) in elementary schools, the use of PMM is still not optimal. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to determine the ability of teachers in using PMM in social studies subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District and to identify the obstacles faced by teachers in using the Merdeka Mengajar Platform. The research method used in this study is a quantitative-exploratory study to describe the ability of teachers in utilizing the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) in social studies subjects in Cluster 3, Pandawan District. Data collection was carried out through observation, interviews, and documentation. Data were analyzed systematically using qualitative data analysis techniques, including data preparation, building data understanding, data coding, descriptions and themes, and presentation of findings. The results of the study showed that the majority of teachers have been able to utilize the basic features of PMM, but there are still several obstacles that need to be overcome. The results of the study showed that the majority of teachers have been able to utilize the basic features of PMM, but there are still several obstacles that need to be overcome. Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that the potential of PMM in improving the quality of social studies learning in Elementary Schools is very good. However, the success of PMM implementation still faces several obstacles that need to be overcome such as limited internet access, lack of technological knowledge, time constraints and lack of motivation. The recommendations proposed, such as ongoing training, improving infrastructure related to internet access, and establishing a teacher community, are expected to overcome existing obstacles and maximize the potential of PMM in improving the quality of learning.

KEYWORDS:

Reconstruction, Improvement, PMM, teacher ability.

Corresponding Author: Anggriyani

**Cite this Article: Anggriyani, Bulkani (2024). Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District. International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies, 4(11), 1247-1256*

A. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 requires teachers to use technology in classroom learning. However, there are difficulties for teachers in applying the application, namely: (1) teachers have difficulty in adapting to technological developments; (2) classroom learning must be adaptive; (3) teachers have

Anggriyani et al, Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District

difficulty adapting to technology; and (4) teachers have difficulty in utilizing existing technology. One of the applications used by teachers in sharing good practices is that teachers must use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM), this application is a development provided by the Ministry of Education and Culture, as one of the suggestions prepared by the government in implementing classroom learning. The Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology presents the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) as an innovative application specifically designed to help teachers improve the quality of learning in Indonesia. PMM facilitates teachers in various aspects, from teaching, improving competence, to working more optimally. PMM is designed by utilizing modern technology, aiming to expand access to education. PMM was developed to be a partner for teachers in implementing the independent curriculum with a spirit of collaboration and sharing. (Kemendikbud Ristek 2022). PMM can be said to be an educational "super app" because it contains various features that support teaching and learning activities, including: (a) learning resources, PMM provides access to various articles, learning videos, and examples of teaching tools, teachers can use them as inspiration and references in preparing teaching materials, (b) training, PMM offers training programs to help teachers improve their teaching competencies, (c) assessment analysis through PMM, teachers can get the results of student assessment analysis that can be used to plan learning that is in accordance with student needs, (d) sharing community, PMM provides a space for teachers to share experiences and best teaching practices. By accessing the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM), teachers can provide an understanding of matters related to the independent curriculum (Sofyan., et al 2023). Overall, PMM aims to make it easier for teachers to teach according to the abilities and needs of students, provide a forum for developing teacher competencies, and foster a spirit of collaboration and sharing among teachers.

One of the main objectives of PMM is to improve the quality of education in Indonesia, especially in areas that are less accessible by adequate educational facilities. The Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) Platform is expected to improve teacher competence, foster a spirit of collaboration and sharing among teachers, research results show that through the Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) Platform, competence can be improved (Aulia., et al 2023). From the official website managed by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (2022), the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) program bridges the educational gap which can be directly accessed through (<https://guru.kemdikbud.go.id/>) by using a learning id account. PMM opens equal access for all teachers in Indonesia, both in big cities and in remote areas to learn, teach, and work. Teachers need to improve the quality of learning in the classroom and utilize the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) because in addition to providing interesting

and very helpful features for teachers (Iskandar., et al 2023). Other things that can be utilized include: (a) supporting the implementation of the independent curriculum by providing various learning resources and references that are in line with the independent curriculum, such as teaching modules, learning videos, and examples of teaching tools (Romanti., 2023) and is expected to help teachers understand and implement the independent curriculum in the classroom more easily and effectively, (b) improve teacher competence, by offering various training programs and professional development for teachers, such as training on the use of technology in learning, the latest pedagogy, and student assessment, (c) facilitate learning preparation, by providing various learning resources that teachers can use to prepare for learning in the classroom, such as articles, learning videos, and examples of teaching tools (Wiguna., 2024), teachers can access learning resources easily and quickly through the PMM application, (d) conduct student assessments, by providing assessment tools that teachers can use to measure student learning achievement, assessment results can be used by teachers to plan more focused learning and in accordance with student needs (Kateren., et al 2022), (e) sharing best practices, by providing a platform for teachers to share best practices in learning and can use them to learn from the experiences of other teachers and improve the quality of learning in the classroom, (f) increasing collaboration between teachers, teachers collaborate and work together in developing learning in the classroom.

Teachers can share learning resources with each other, discuss best practices, and help each other solve learning problems based on performance reports (Kemendikbud Ristek 2022). To maximize the potential of PPM in advancing education, an integrated strategy is needed that equips teachers with technological skills and the ability to adapt to learning methods that are in accordance with PMM (Aulia., et al 2023). Kemendikbud Ristek (2022) put forward the important role of teachers in using and optimizing PMM at this time, namely: (1). As agents of change, teachers are agents of change in the national education system, and PMM provides the tools and resources needed for agents with innovative new curricula and teaching methods; (2). Collaborative learning ecosystem, teachers interact with each other on the PMM platform, share effective learning methods and best practices, and contribute to the development of new teaching materials; (3). Standardization of education quality, by providing wider access for teachers to take part in government-organized training and develop their competencies; (4) Content contributors, almost 100% of learning content on the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) is contributed by educators and content contributors who actively participate, they contribute by creating teaching modules, teaching materials, and project modules that are in accordance with the independent curriculum, improving the quality of education in Indonesia as a whole, educators can

Anggriyani et al, Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District

share their knowledge and experience, and improve the quality of the learning materials presented; (5). Building a learning community, by facilitating interaction and collaboration between teachers through participatory features such as “Evidence of performance” and “Best practices”, teachers can exchange ideas, share teaching experiences, and get inspiration from the best practices of their peers.

The fact is that currently synchronization between teachers and technology is the key to success in the learning process. In his research, he revealed that alignment between technology and teachers is very necessary in the learning process (Rahmawati., et al 2020). Teachers not only need to master the subject matter, but also must be able to utilize various types of technology to support teaching and learning activities, so that students can get a more interesting, interactive, and meaningful learning experience. The Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) Platform is the main weapon in facing the independent curriculum (Wahyuningsih., 2022). The Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) Platform has begun to be used by teachers in elementary schools, helping educators gain an understanding of references and inspiration to be able to implement the independent curriculum. Currently, the use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform in improving the abilities of teachers and students in elementary schools can be felt (Arnest., et al 2023).

Education using technology can have a positive influence on teaching and learning activities in a more advanced direction (Rahmalia., 2020). The survey of the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (2023) showed a significant increase in teacher awareness and abilities related to PMM, the majority of teachers now know PMM and are able to access it, their basic ability to search for information is getting better, with ease in finding teaching modules, assessments, and other learning resources. The Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) Platform is designed to support more active and student-centered learning, behind its success there are still a number of challenges that need to be considered, especially in implementation in the field. The Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (2020) case study shows that teachers still tend to rely on textbooks in teaching, this indicates that teachers have not fully utilized the potential of PMM in providing a variety of learning resources, many teachers in remote areas are still lagging behind in terms of readiness to connect technology in learning, especially teachers in 3T areas are still constrained in implementing science and technology optimally (Mutia., et al 2023).

This case occurred in the use of PMM for social studies learning in elementary schools in Hulu Sungai Tengah Regency, especially in Pandawan District, namely the use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) in Social Sciences (IPS) subjects in elementary schools is still not optimal. Yulianto & Wibowo (2018) stated that there are still obstacles in the implementation of educational technology in

Indonesia. Similar research on the use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) has also been conducted by Marisana & Kurniawan (2023) where researchers aimed to analyze the use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) to improve teacher competence with research results showing that PMM is an important and helpful tool in the learning process of elementary school teachers. PMM offers various features that help teachers hone their skills, increase their insights, and gain innovation and creative ideas, but the main weakness of PMM is the lack of fluency of teachers in using it. In the research of Arnes., et al (2023) by analyzing the use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) by PPKn teachers to accelerate the implementation of the independent curriculum which aims to find out in depth how PMM helps teachers in the teaching and learning process and the implementation of the independent curriculum, this study states that the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) has been utilized by PPKn teachers of Public Middle Schools throughout Sijunjung Regency to accelerate the implementation of the independent curriculum, many benefits of PMM are felt by teachers from the use of PMM, including getting inspiration and good teaching and learning practices from quality videos, creating innovative learning works, documenting the work of teachers and students, sharing work results with colleagues throughout Indonesia, getting feedback from more advanced colleagues, interacting with various teacher communities, conducting assessments of students, getting the latest references and various teaching tools, this study also recommends that PMM access is also provided to lecturers and researchers, so that they can build an Indonesian education ecosystem.

Based on similar research above, this research has never been conducted before, research on teachers' ability to use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) in social studies subjects in elementary schools throughout Pandawan District has an important reason, namely this research focuses on the use of PMM for social studies subjects in elementary schools. Social studies is considered very appropriate for the independent curriculum because as a subject of learning, social studies aims to produce citizens who have knowledge and understanding of society and the nation and have social and even emotional skills and abilities in order to be able to contribute to the development of social and cultural life (Jumriani., et al 2021). Previous research only examined the use of PMM in general or in other subjects, while this research focuses on the formulation of the problem of how teachers' ability to use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) in social studies subjects in elementary schools throughout Pandawan District, with the aim of determining teachers' ability to use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) and identifying the obstacles faced by teachers in using the Merdeka Mengajar Platform. There is great hope for changes in the use of PMM, so that after this research, teachers can improve their understanding of how PMM can

Anggriyani et al, Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District

be used effectively in social studies learning, so that they can improve the quality of learning and student learning outcomes.

B. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach and descriptive-explorative methods, which were carried out from July 2024 to September 2024 in cluster 3, Pandawan District, this study involved 24 social studies subject teachers in high classes as research subjects. The teachers came from 8 schools in cluster 3, Pandawan District, considering the ease of access and data collection, because they are in close proximity and easy to reach. The selection of subjects from each category was taken by 3 high-class teachers to be used as research subjects with the criteria being high-class teachers for each school, able to communicate both verbally and in writing and asking for consideration from the principal. Data collection techniques in the study were observation, interviews, and documentation, researchers conducted observations to obtain initial information about teachers' abilities in utilizing PPM in classroom learning in social studies subjects, because observation is one of the variants of data collection method options that has a strong methodological character (Hasanah., 2017). Furthermore, the interviews conducted began with the following stages:

- a. Conducting interviews, namely to determine the teacher's ability to use PMM, interviews are conducted on subjects after the observation instrument.
- b. The data obtained in question are the results of interviews and observation results.
- c. Researchers as the main instrument conduct observations, analyze research data, interpret research data and make conclusions.
- d. Collecting data through focused discussions, aiming to find meaning related to the formulation of the problems raised.

The development of supporting instruments in this study is an interview guideline, and small notes during data collection, the interview guideline contains the main questions developed by the interviewer in conducting the interview, the interview was conducted to clarify/explore the problem of teacher ability in using and identifying obstacles faced by teachers in using the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools throughout Pandawan District. In unstructured interviews, questions are prepared in advance, but when in the field, the questions are adjusted to the unique circumstances and characteristics of the respondents.

The data analysis technique used from data collection is the results of researcher observations as the main instrument, and interviews as stated above and then analyzed. Qualitative data analysis according to Creswell (2010) is a systematic process consisting of five main steps: data preparation, building data understanding, data coding, description and

themes, and presentation of findings. Data interpretation is an important part of qualitative data analysis to produce valid and meaningful findings. To increase the validity and reliability of this study, data verification techniques were added using triangulation techniques, by comparing data obtained from observations, interviews, and documents, comparing the results of observations on the frequency of use of PMM with teacher statements in interviews.

The research procedure is divided into several stages: research preparation, at this preparation stage activities are carried out including (1) perfecting the proposal, (2) preparing valid or validated instruments, (3) preparing data collection tools and (4) conditioning the teachers involved in the data collection process:

1. Data collection or implementation of research, namely conducting in-depth interviews, and observation results, exploring research problems and developing research instruments, at this stage the researcher also selects research subjects in each category;
2. Data analysis is the activity of transcribing, categorizing data, reducing data, checking the validity of data, reviewing data and describing teachers' abilities in using the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) in social studies subjects in elementary schools in Pandawan District;
3. The activity in the final stage is after the research results are obtained, continued by writing a research report.

Triangulation is carried out to test the credibility of data or trust in data. Miles and Huberman (1994) put forward three types of triangulation, namely (1) triangulation of data sources (triangulation by data source) which includes, people, places, and others (2) triangulation of methods (triangulation by method) includes observation, interviews, and documentation. This method of triangulation is also often referred to as constant comparison; (3) triangulation of time (triangulation by researcher) includes investigator A, B, and so on. Sugiyono (2008), Triangulation in testing data credibility is interpreted as checking data from various sources, various methods, and various times. Thus there are three types of triangulation, namely (1) triangulation of sources, (2) triangulation of techniques/data collection methods, and (3) triangulation of time. The triangulation used in this study is triangulation of techniques, with in-depth interviews, and observation results.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Research result

Teachers' ability to use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform From the results of the study of 24 teachers, data collection from interviews with respondents to dig deeper into their understanding of the use of PMM, based on the results of the interviews, it was found that most teachers had understood the basics of using PMM, but some respondents stated that they did not master all the features available in PMM. their

Anggriyani et al, Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District

skills still vary, they have varying levels of mastery of PMM, especially in the teaching menu, the features in the teaching menu consist of achievements (CP) and learning objective flows (ATP), teaching tools, student assessments, and classes, from observations it can be seen that some teachers are able to access and utilize these features such as making lesson plans and downloading teaching materials. There are some teachers who have not mastered more complex features, such as creating teaching modules and creating assessments. Some teachers have succeeded in integrating PMM into their learning such as delivering materials and giving assignments, but there are still teachers who have difficulty practicing it in the learning process. From observations it can be seen that some teachers have not consistently used PMM in learning activities, only a small number of teachers are active, and only a few create content or share good practices.

Results of observations of several respondents in using PMM in social studies subjects

Figure 1. PMM display on learning resource features

Description: Teachers have been able to utilize the learning resource feature by successfully finding several learning videos that are relevant to social studies subjects. This is relevant to the results of interviews and observations, which show that a number of teachers, 13 out of 24 respondents, have successfully utilized the learning resource feature on the Merdeka Mengajar Platform. These teachers, identified with codes A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, were able to find learning videos as supporting learning materials for social studies subjects. This finding indicates that teachers already have basic skills in using and have begun to utilize PMM as an effective learning resource in supporting the learning process

Figure 2. PMM display on the learning resources feature

Description: Teachers have utilized the learning features on PMM by successfully downloading teaching materials, which are used as teaching materials for social studies subjects. This is relevant to the results of interviews and observations, namely although not all teachers have utilized all the features available on PMM, there are positive indications regarding the utilization of the teaching material download feature, it was found that several teachers identified with codes N, O, P, Q, R, S, 6 out of 24 teachers have the ability to download complete teaching materials consisting of material references, learning media, exercises and assessments, and other teaching materials, this shows an active effort in utilizing PMM as a learning resource.

Figure 3. PMM display on the evidence of work feature

Note: Teachers have successfully created and uploaded good learning practices and practices on the evidence of work feature. This is relevant to the results of interviews and observations, namely that a small number of 2 out of 24 teachers identified with codes T and U have been known to be able to utilize the evidence of work feature by sharing their best learning practices. The results of interviews and

Anggriyani et al, Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District

observations confirm this finding, where these teachers voluntarily share their experiences and innovations in the learning process through PMM.

Figure 4.1

Figure 4.2

Teacher activities when using and utilizing features on PMM
 Description: In Figure 4.1, it shows that teachers already understand how to use and utilize the PMM feature in the lesson plan by creating teaching materials for social studies subjects. In Figure 4.2, it shows that teachers have not fully mastered the PMM feature in the lesson plan because they still seem to have difficulty in determining specific learning objectives. This is relevant to the results of interviews and observations, namely that most teachers have not fully mastered the feature, as seen in Figures 4.1 and 4.2, only a few 3 out of 24 teachers identified with codes V, W, X have been able and have been able to create complete and structured teaching materials such as teaching modules, teaching materials and learning projects. This data strengthens the finding that efforts need to be made to improve teacher competence in using PMM.

Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.2

Teacher activities when utilizing PMM and applying it to classroom learning

Description: Figure 5.1 shows that teachers have utilized the features in the teaching menu, although not fully. Figure 5.2 shows that teachers have fully succeeded in integrating PMM into learning. The results of a study of 24 teachers through interviews and observations showed variations in their ability to utilize the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM). Although some teachers have succeeded in fully integrating PMM into the learning process as seen in Figure 5.2, most teachers are still in the exploration stage of the available features, as shown in Figure 5.2, the main obstacles faced by teachers include limited internet access, lack of technological knowledge, time constraints, and lack of motivation. Observation instrument for mastery of the Merdeka. PMM features to one of the respondents. Aims to collect direct data regarding mastery of several PMM features.

Table 1: Results of Observations on Mastery of Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) Platform Features

No	Fitur PMM	Observed Actions	Time Spent	Notes
1	Search for Learning Resources	Looking for learning videos about royal historical heritage	5 minutes	Found some relevant videos
2	Search for Learning Resources	Download teaching materials on the theme of historical heritage of the kingdom	5 menit	Successfully downloaded one learning material
3	Lesson Plan	Creating a lesson plan for the theme of historical heritage of the kingdom	10 minutes	Having difficulty in determining specific learning objectives
4	Student Assessment	Uploading daily assessment questions	10 minutes	Having an error uploading files

Of the 24 respondents with mastery of PMM features, 54% (13 people) have searched for learning resources, 25% (6 people) have downloaded teaching materials, 13% (3 people)

have created teaching materials, and 8% (2 people) have shared good practices, as seen in the diagram below.

Diagram 1.3. Observation Results of Mastery of Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM)

Features 2. Obstacles faced by teachers in using the Merdeka Mengajar Platform Based on the results of in-depth interviews with all respondents regarding the use of features on the PMM, researchers interacted with teachers during observations to obtain more indepth information to reveal several obstacles faced by respondents, namely due to lack of technological knowledge including the reasons why they do not understand how to use PMM, most respondents answered that the obstacles to using PMM were due to limited internet access which was less stable in several schools, then lack of time for teachers because in addition to the teaching burden,

the administrative burden was also a reason, as well as other problems including lack of motivation from the teacher. Of the 24 respondents, almost half had internet access constraints of 46% (11 people), did not understand 8.4% (2 people), with time constraints of 16.6% (4 people) and with other constraints of 29% (7 people).

The observation instrument for observing the use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) aims to collect direct data regarding the constraints faced by teachers in using PMM during the learning process.

Table 2: Constraints faced by teachers in using the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM)

No	Aspects observed	Constraint categories	Description (examples of actions, speech, etc.)
1	Technical Skills	Not really understand	a. Teachers have difficulty accessing certain features on PMM, for example searching for learning materials. b. Teachers ask colleagues about how to use certain features
2	Internet Access	Connection unstable	a. The teacher experiences slow loading when accessing PMM. b. The teacher decides not to use PMM because the internet connection is lost.
3	Time	Limited	a. Teachers only use PMM briefly because they are in a hurry to prepare other materials. b. Teachers complain about not having enough time to explore PMM features.
4	Other obstacles (motivation)	Low	a. Teachers seem less enthusiastic in using PMM. b. Teachers more often use conventional learning methods.

Diagram 1.4. Obstacles faced by teachers in using the Merdeka Mengajar Platform

D. DISCUSSION

After collecting data from observations and in-depth interviews, the researcher then compared the consistency of the data and the results that could strengthen the use of PMM in this study. It can be concluded that the use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform by teachers is still at various stages. Although most teachers have understood the basics of using PMM, mastery of more complex features, such as creating teaching modules and assessments, is still a challenge. The study showed that when teachers use this platform effectively, students become more enthusiastic in learning social studies, as seen from the increase in student participation and motivation during learning activities using PMM. This finding is in line with previous research that technology increases student motivation and engagement, improves teaching quality, and expands access to information. Technology also allows for personalization of learning that suits individual needs (Turnip., et al 2023).

In accordance with the theory of constructivism which focuses on learning in networks and how knowledge develops through connections, technology has a central role in connecting individuals with relevant information and resources, this theory supports the concept of TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge), teachers who are able to master technology, pedagogy, and content can create a more effective and interesting learning experience for students. In this theory, it is argued that teachers are not only able to master subject matter and teaching methods, but are also able to integrate technology effectively in the learning process, by understanding the theory underlying TPACK, teachers can better integrate technology in learning and improve student learning outcomes. Teachers who are able to use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) demonstrate a good understanding of technology, teachers can operate the platform, access various features, and use them for learning purposes.

Several important points to note from the results of this study are that in terms of feature mastery, there are significant

differences among teachers, the majority of teachers more often search for and download teaching materials, while those who create their own teaching materials or share good practices are still relatively few. In line with the research of Cahyani., et al (2020) who have conducted an analysis of teacher problems in using the Merdeka Mengajar platform, that the obstacles faced by teachers in using PMM are lack of technological knowledge, limited internet access, lack of time, and lack of motivation. Although some teachers have succeeded in integrating PMM into their learning, many still have difficulty practicing it consistently (Kemendikbud Ristek 2022).

The ability of teachers to use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) is greatly influenced by factors such as the lack of intensive training on the use of PMM, the availability of stable internet access and adequate devices are also very important to support the use of PMM (Cahyani., et al 2020), the heavy workload of teachers, both in terms of teaching and administration, can reduce the time available to study and use PMM and internal motivation of teachers and support from the work environment also play an important role in encouraging the use of PMM.

E. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusion

- Teachers' ability to use the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) in social studies subjects in elementary schools throughout Pandawan District varies, the majority of teachers have been able to utilize basic features on the teaching menu such as the CP/ATP feature (Learning achievements/Learning objective flow), teaching tools (containing teaching resources and teaching materials) and evidence of work (containing work, learning practices and good practices);
- The potential of PMM in improving the quality of learning in social studies subjects in Pandawan District is very large;

Anggriyani et al, Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District

- Improvement has a very large role that is needed by teachers in efforts to overcome major obstacles such as limited internet access, lack of technological knowledge, time constraints and lack of motivation faced by teachers.

2. Recommendations

- More structured and sustainable training on the use of PMM, in improving government infrastructure;
- Schools need to ensure the availability of stable internet access and adequate devices in all schools, and strive for community development, as well as the need to build a community of PMM-using teachers who share knowledge and experiences, so that they can support and motivate each other.

F. GRATITUDE IS EXPRESSED TO

1. Muhammadiyah University of Palangkaraya for providing the opportunity to continue my Masters studies;
2. Principal of Elementary School 1 Setiap of Pndawa, South Kalimantan, who has given permission to continue my studies at Muhadiyah University. Indonesia;
3. Thesis Supervisor Prof. Dr. Bulkani, M.Pd. who has provided motivation during the guidance, so that the thesis can be completed properly

REFERENCES

1. Abdurahman, I. S., & Pujiastuti, H. (2024). Educational Transformation Through Innovation With Analysis of Experience Using the Merdeka Mengajar (Pmm) Platform in the Learning Process. *Pendas: Scientific Journal of Elementary Education*, 9(1), 1422-1432.
2. Admin Sekolah.Net, (2023, Oktober). Merdeka Mengajar Platform: Makes it Easier for Educators to Improve the Quality of Learning. <https://adminsekolah.net/platform-merdeka-mengajar-mudahkan-pendidik-menigkatkankualitas-pembelajaran>
3. Ambawani, C. S. L., Kusuma, T. M. M., Utama, S., & Sumardjoko, B. (2023). Faktor Penyebab Rendahnya Akses Platform Merdeka Mengajar (PMM). *Journal of Education Research*, 4(4), 1880-1892.
4. Anggraini, G., & Winarti, W. (2023). Problems Using the Free Teaching Platform for Teachers in Areas Without an Electric Network (Study at SMPN Satu Atap 2 Mentaya Hulu). *Bitnet: Journal of Information Technology Education*, 8(2), 103112.
5. Arnes, A., Musparidi, M., & Yusmanila, Y. (2023). Analysis of the Utilization of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform by PPKn Teachers to Accelerate the Implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum. *Edukatif: Journal of Educational Sciences*, 5(1), 60-70.
6. Aulia, D., Murni, I., & Desyandri, D. (2023). Improving the competence of elementary school teachers through the independent teaching platform (PMM). *Scientific Journal of Educational Profession*, 8(1b), 800-807.
7. Azhar, M., (2023, Nopember,20). The Merdeka Mengajar platform makes teachers transform education <https://govinsider.asia/indo-en/article/platform-merdekamengajar-jadikan-guru-sebagai-agen-transformasi-pendidikan>
8. Platform Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) in Elementary Schools. In *Social, Humanities, and Educational Studies (SHES): Conference Series* (Vol. 7, No. 3).
9. Dewi, S. E., Santoso, A., & Dewi, R. S. I. (2024). Analysis of the Use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform to Support the Optimization of Merdeka Belajar at the Elementary School Level. *Al-Madrasah: Journal of Elementary Madrasah Education*, 8(1), 350-361.
10. Cahyani, R. Y., Latifah, R., & Risky, S. A. Implementation Analysis and Problematics for Teachers in the Use of the Platform Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) in Elementary Schools. In *Social, Humanities, and Educational Studies (SHES): Conference Series* (Vol. 7, No. 3).
11. Hasanah, H. (2017). Observation techniques (an alternative method of qualitative data collection in the social sciences). *At-Taqaddum*, 8(1), 21-46.
12. Iskandar, S., Rosmana, P. S., Azizah, A., Fazriyah, A., Febriana, N., & Prayogo, R. S. (2023). Iskandar, S., Rosmana, P. S., Nisa, F. F., Nisrina, F. A., Oktaviani, O., & Realistiya, R. (2023). Implementation of Independent Curriculum in Grade IV of Elementary School in Purwakarta Regency. *Innovative: Journal Of Social Science Research*, 3(2), 1658-1667.
13. Iskandar, S., Rosmana, P. S., Nisa, F. F., Nisrina, F. A., Oktaviani, O., & Realistiya, R. (2023). The Use of the Merdeka Mengajar Platform as a Means for Teachers in Understanding the Merdeka Curriculum. *Innovative: Journal of Social Science Research*, 3(2), 1301-1306.
14. Isnaini, E. (2022). Clinical Supervision of Pmm Utilization to Improve Teachers' Ability to Compile Teaching Modules for Grade IV SDN Sisir 01 Batu District for the 2022/2023 Academic Year. *Taman Widya Humaniora Education Journal*, 1(3), 398-419.
15. Jumriani, J., Syaharuddin, S., Hadi, N. T. F. W., Mutiani, M., & Abbas, E. W. (2021). Literature Review; Components of Social Studies Curriculum

Anggriyani et al, Reconstruction of Improving Teachers' Ability in Using The Independent Teaching Platform (PMM) Application in Social Studies Subjects in Elementary Schools in Pandawan District

- in Elementary Schools in the Curriculum 2013. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 5(4), 2027-2035.
16. Lena, M. S., Nisa, S., Putri, O. K., & Husna, R. H. (2023). The Use of the Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) Platform to Improve Teacher Competence in Elementary Schools. *Badge: Journal of Educational Science Innovation*, 1(3), 177-185.
 17. Marisana, D., Iskandar, S., & Kurniawan, D. T. (2023). The use of the Merdeka Teaching platform to improve teacher competence in elementary schools. *Basicedu Journal*, 7(1), 139-150. *Merdeka. Educational Studies in Various Aspects*, 99.
 18. Moleong, L. J. (2019). *Metodologi penelitian kualitatif*. PT Remaja Rosdakarya Bandung.
 19. Mutia, I. K., Wosal, Y. N., & Monigir, N. N. (2023). Teacher Readiness in Facing Educational Challenges in the Field of Science and Technology. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 7(6), 3571-3579.
 20. Partikasari, R., Haryono, M., Imran, R. F., Pebriani, E., & Oktasari, S. (2023). Optimizing the use of the Merdeka Teaching platform and strengthening P5 for teachers in the North Bengkulu I Regional Coordinator. *Dehasen Journal for the Country*, 2(1), 47-52.
 21. Prasetyaningsih, N., Muiz, A., & Fatimah, F. (2024). PUsing the Merdeka Mengajar Platform (PMM) to Improve Teacher Competence in Primary Schools. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 8(1), 788-798.
 22. Pratama, M. A. (2023). Peran Model Project Based Learning dalam Penerapan Kurikulum Merdeka. *Kajian Pendidikan dalam Berbagai Aspek*, 99.
 23. Rahmawati, A., Suryani, N., Akhyar, M., & Sukarmin. (2020). Technology-Integrated Project-Based Learning for Pre-Service Teacher Education: A Systematic Literature Review. *Open Engineering*, 10(1), 620-629.
 24. Ramdani, M., Yuliyanti, S. Y., Rahmatulloh, I. T., & Suratman, S. (2022). Penggunaan Platform merdeka mengajar (PMM) pada guru sekolah dasar. *Journal of Instructional and Development Researches*, 2(6), 248-254.
 25. Romanti, (2023, Agustus). Peran Platform Merdeka Mengajar (PMM) dalam Implementasi Kurikulum Merdeka
<https://itjen.kemdikbud.go.id/web/peranplatform-merdeka-mengajar-pmm-dalam-implementasi-kurikulum-merdeka/>.
 26. Sugiyono, D. (2013). Educational research methods quantitative, qualitative and R&D approaches.
 27. Turnip, R. S. (2023). Increasing Digital Literacy Among Students: Introduction and Practice of Using Educational Technology. *Journal of Education and Teaching Review (JRPP)*, 6(4), 2302-2310.
 28. Wardana, M. A. W., Indra, D. P., & Ulya, C. (2023). Analysis of the Use of the Merdeka Belajar Application by Indonesian Language Teachers at Surakarta Junior High Schools as an Acceleration of the Implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum. *Journal of Indonesian Language and Literature Education Undiksha*, 13(3).
 29. Yuniarsih, W. (2024, April). Implementation of the Independent Teaching Platform
<https://www.suaramuhammadiyah.id/read/implemptasi-platform-merdekamengajar>.